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BIOPIGEE

Model Output: Number of human cases with and without biosecurity measures

Participating countries

UK (APHA), FR (ANSES), SE (SVA)

1. Introduction

Salmonella and Hepatitis E virus (HEV) are zoonotic pathogens which are in general subclinical in pigs. With 52,702 confirmed cases of human salmonellosis and 57 deaths in the EU in 2020, salmonellosis was the second most reported foodborne gastrointestinal infection in humans after campylobacteriosis (EFSA 2020). Typical symptoms range from diarrhoea, fever, and abdominal cramps. Most healthy people recover within a week without treatment, however, in some cases, dehydration due to severe or prolonged diarrhoea can require medical attention. Life-threatening complications may develop if the infection spreads beyond the intestines. *Salmonella* caused 22.5% of all foodborne outbreaks in 2020 in EU with “pig meat and products thereof” ranking second, after “eggs and egg product”, amongst the food products most involved as the source of *Salmonella* infection (EFSA 2020).

Salmonella is a long-standing problem within the pig industry and many countries, particularly in the north of the EU (Bonardi 2021), have implemented farm-level surveillance and control strategies in the last 20 years with differing degrees of success (Correia-Gomes 2021); to date, there is still high a proportion of *Salmonella* positive carcasses and many herds still have high *Salmonella* prevalence and seroprevalence (EFSA & ECDC 2017).

Hepatitis E is considered an emerging zoonotic disease in the EU and although infection is normally self-limiting, it can lead to liver failure – which can be fatal – in immunocompromised individuals, or those with pre-existing liver conditions. More than 21,000 (mostly locally acquired) HEV clinical cases with 28 fatalities have been recorded in the EU/EEA between 2007 and 2017. Genotypes 3 and 4 (HEV-G3, -G4) are those most commonly associated with autochthonous cases in Europe and are zoonotic, infecting swine, wild boar, and occasionally other animal species such as rabbit and deer. HEV-G3 is the most frequent genotype found in Suidae and from the epidemiological evidence consistently identifying exposure to pigs or pork products as risk factors for human infection, foodborne transmission appears to be a major route for HEV infection in the EU with HEV-G3 being the most frequently implicated genotype (EFSA 2017).

Being a relatively new problem, farm level risk factors for HEV infection in pigs have rarely been investigated. The virus is transmitted by the faecal-oral route and large viral loads have been observed in the faeces (Salines 2017), contributing to environmental contamination. Farm internal biosecurity measures may have a role in limiting occurrence, persistence, and transmission of the virus in farms, but how and which measures may influence this is largely unknown.

Given that the consumption of pork products is a significant driver for the risk of human exposure to both *Salmonella* and HEV, adoption of biosecurity protocols to prevent infection of pigs and/or reduce the level of contamination in infected animals and food products along the food chain is key to mitigate the risk of human exposure and infection to both pathogens.

The BIOPIGEE project aims to review and generate additional knowledge on effective as well as cost-effective biosecurity measures for *Salmonella* and HEV that can inform practical decisions about implementing further measures to reduce herd prevalence and the risk for consumers. The overarching aim of work package 4 of the One Health European Joint Programme funded project BIOPIGEE is to assess the cost-effectiveness of standard and specific biosecurity measures in relation to the prevalence reduction of *Salmonella* and HEV, as well as their impact on the final risk to consumers. This includes development of quantitative models to simulate the effectiveness of biosecurity measures. In this report for deliverable D-JRP21-WP4.17 we discuss the development of a quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA), with specific objectives to simulate

- (i) Baseline model: the number of human *Salmonella* and hepatitis E cases due to consumption of pork products
- (ii) Biosecurity measures: the reduction in the number of cases following adoption of biosecurity measures

Results of this deliverable are being used to inform an economic model aimed to assess the economic profitability associated with implementing the specific intervention measures (deliverable D-JRP21-WP4.16).

2. Methods

2.1. Baseline model

The expected number of human *Salmonella* and hepatitis E cases due to consumption of pork products was simulated by adapting a comprehensive farm-to-consumption QMRA for *Salmonella* in pigs, which was a Monte Carlo (MC) simulation previously developed for the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) (EFSA 2010, Snary 2016). An overview of the main steps included in the QMRAs for *Salmonella* and HEV is provided by the flowchart shown in Fig. 1.

Taking the prevalence of infected pigs entering the slaughter line as an input, the annual number of human *Salmonella* and HEV infections are estimated by simulating the fate of the two pathogens during slaughtering, processing, and preparation and consumption of the following products: fermented sausage (FS), minced meat (MM), pork chops (PC), liver pâté (LP) and sliced liver (SL). The *Salmonella* model considers the products FS, MM and PC, while the HEV model considers LP, MM and SL, since pork liver products are known to carry a relatively high risk of hepatitis E infection (Pavio 2014).

The model for *Salmonella* was based on data from Austria and the UK, and results were presented for these two countries. The model for HEV was parameterised using data from France. For *Salmonella*, the prevalence of infected pigs entering the slaughter line was taken from the published literature, using values of 2% for Austria (Kostenzer 2014) and 32.2% for the UK (Martelli 2021); prevalence estimates for HEV were obtained from a farm model developed as part of BIOPIGEE deliverable D-JRP21-WP4.11, which was parameterised for France (Salines 2020a, Salines 2020b). This model

combines an on-farm transmission model (SimInf) with a between-herd exponential random graph/network model, predicting an average prevalence of pigs shedding HEV RNA in their faeces of 5.9% on arrival at French slaughterhouses.

Fig. 1. Flowchart outlining the pathways considered in the QMRA for both *Salmonella* and HEV.

For both *Salmonella* and HEV, the model considers events that affect both the presence and amount of the pathogens along the food chain, starting at the slaughterhouse and ending at consumption. At this point, we then simulate the dose ingested and the expected number of human cases (including asymptomatic infection) for each of the selected products.

2.1.1. Review of *Salmonella* QMRA

The mathematical details of the baseline *Salmonella* model framework, which are here also adapted to HEV, can be found in the collection of papers describing the EFSA risk assessment (Swart 2016a, Swart 2016b, Vigre 2016). Briefly, the *Slaughter & Further Processing* module describes, in a highly mechanistic manner, the effect of each processing stage on the presence and amount of bacteria moving between the carcass and environment (Swart 2016a). In the *Preparation & Consumption* module, the impact of transport, storage, and meal preparation (including bacterial growth and cross-contamination) on the prevalence and load of bacteria ingested by consumers is simulated (Swart 2016b). Finally, whether the ingested dose leads to infection is simulated through a dose-response

model for *Salmonella* (Vigre 2016). Readers are invited to refer to the original papers for a comprehensive presentation of the methods, however, for completeness a brief summary including a narrative description of the events and the parameters considered in the QMRA for *Salmonella* are reported in Table 1. Adaptations that are necessary to model HEV rather than *Salmonella*, as well as new features of the QMRA introduced to model the two new liver products, are described in detail in the subsequent sections.

Table 1. Summary of modules and stages of Salmonella QMRA, including outputs and relevant references.

Module	Stage	Description	Output	Reference
Slaughterhouse	Bleeding	Not modelled.	Microbial contamination on each carcass	Swart 2016a
	Scalding	<p><i>Salmonella</i> load on carcass hide is modelled as a function of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial load - <i>Salmonella</i> inactivation rate in water/on skin at temperature of scalding bath - Time spent in scalding bath - Fraction of <i>Salmonella</i> transferred from skin to water - Attachment rate of <i>Salmonella</i> in water to skin (allows for cross contamination) 		
	Dehairing	<p><i>Salmonella</i> load on carcass hide is modelled as a function of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial load - Amount of faeces extruded - Concentration of <i>Salmonella</i> in faeces - Time spent in the dehairing machine - Fraction of <i>Salmonella</i> transferred from skin to machine - Attachment rate of <i>Salmonella</i> in machine to skin 		
	Singeing	<p><i>Salmonella</i> load on carcass hide is modelled as a function of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial load - <i>Salmonella</i> inactivation rate in singeing machine - Time spent in the singeing machine 		
	Polishing	<i>Salmonella</i> load on carcass hide is modelled as for dehairing.		
	Belly opening	<p><i>Salmonella</i> load on carcass hide is modelled as a function of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial load - Fraction of <i>Salmonella</i> transferred from skin to hook - Incision length and width - Surface area of carcass - Probability of puncturing gut - Amount of faeces spilled from gut - Concentration of <i>Salmonella</i> in faeces 		

		- Fraction of spilled faeces transferred to hook	Microbial contamination on each half carcass	
	Splitting	<p><i>Salmonella</i> load on half-carcass hide is modelled as a function of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial load on carcass hide - Fraction of <i>Salmonella</i> transferred to saw - Length of carcass - Width of saw - Surface area of carcass 		
	Trimming	<p><i>Salmonella</i> load on half-carcass hide is modelled as a function of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The total amount of visible faecal material - Concentration of <i>Salmonella</i> in faeces - Detection limit for faeces on carcass - Number of trimming actions 		
	Blast chilling	1 log ₁₀ reduction assumed for each half carcass.		
Further processing	FS, MM, PC	10,000 portions of each product generated.	Microbial contamination of each portion	N/A
Preparation and consumption	FS	<p>Log reduction of <i>Salmonella</i> during fermentation, drying and storage predicted using polynomial-fit models, which are a function of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pH at the beginning of drying - water activity at the end of drying - storage temperature 	Microbial contamination of each portion	Swart 2016b
	PC	<p>Transport and storage divided into three steps: distribution and retail, transport from retail store to home, and storage in the refrigerator. Bacterial growth is modelled as a function of the time and temperature of each step.</p> <p>Complete inactivation is assumed during cooking, since <i>Salmonella</i> is only present on the outside of the product. <i>Salmonella</i> present on the side dish are modelled as a function of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Probability of preparing a salad - Transfer coefficients from pork chop to knife/cutting board/hands, knife/cutting board/hands to salad, tap to hands and hands to tap 		

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Survival rate on knife/cutting board/hands - Probability of not washing knife/cutting board/hands 		
	MM	<p>Transport and storage, as well as preparation of a salad, modelled as for PC.</p> <p>Spatial temperature distribution of patty during cooking modelled through numerical solution of the heat equation, as a function of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooking time - Frying and ambient temperatures - Thermal properties of patty <p>Result used in combination with <i>Salmonella</i> inactivation rates in ground pork at different temperatures to model bacterial load of each portion.</p>		
Dose response	FS, MM, PC	<p>A probability of infection (including asymptomatic infection) is assigned to each portion of each product according to a Beta-Binomial dose-response model</p> $P_{\text{infection}} = \left[1 - \left(1 + \frac{D}{\beta} \right) \right]^{-\alpha},$ <p>where α and β are parameters and D is the dose of <i>Salmonella</i> ingested.</p>	Probability of infection for each portion	
Human cases	FS, MM, PC	<p>For each product, the number of human cases is calculated as</p> $N = \frac{\langle P_{\text{infection}} \rangle \times m \times 365 \times P}{s},$ <p>where $\langle P_{\text{infection}} \rangle$ is the mean probability of infection over all portions and iterations, m is the amount consumed per person per day, P is the population size and s is the serving size.</p>	Expected human case numbers for each product	Vigre 2016

2.1.2. Adaptation of *Salmonella* QMRA for HEV

Adapting a quantitative model developed for a bacterium to a virus requires consideration of key biological differences in the biology and host-pathogen interaction dynamics that exists between the two pathogens.

The first key difference relates to the host-pathogen interaction dynamics that determines the risk of human exposure due to the consumption of meat products. *Salmonella* is a bacterium that colonizes the intestinal tract of the pig, in particular the ileum, caecum and spiral colon. The main route of transmission is therefore faecal-oral and so for this pathogen, contamination of meat is a result of cross-contamination of the hide of animals and/or carcasses with contaminated faeces. Importantly, the bacteria can survive for a long time in the environment and grow within a wide range of temperatures (6 – 46°C); as such, even a small number of bacteria in meat after processing can result in a high dose at consumption. On the other hand, HEV is an RNA virus known to replicate in the liver and intestine, and therefore can be present in both the faeces and bloodstream of infected animals. Hence, meat can be contaminated by HEV either indirectly (cross-contamination with faeces/bile) or directly, while human exposure due to consumption of liver products is also possible. However, since viruses depend on the protein synthesis mechanisms of their hosts in order to replicate, the viral load can only decrease (by RNA degradation) along the food chain.

In terms of quantitative enumeration, *Salmonella* is a bacterium whose amount of viable bacteria can be directly measured by enumeration of colony-forming units, while HEV is a virus for which most available data are based on PCR measurements quantifying the number of RNA copies present in a sample, rather than the actual amount of infectious virus (the presence of RNA does not necessarily imply that the virus structure to infect a host is intact). Quantifying the amount of actual infectious HEV requires carrying out infectivity assays, which is time consuming and poses methodological challenges (Todt 2020) and this is not normally done when analysing food samples. In the context of a QMRA aiming to estimate the number of human cases, the difference between the detected amount of RNA copies and actual load of infectious virus is key in several aspects:

- i) As observed for other viruses, the relationship between RNA copies and the number of infectious viral particles is most likely not linear (Duggal 2017)
- ii) In terms of log reductions, the response to thermal treatment is not the same for RNA copies and viraemic titre
- iii) The probability of infection should be calculated in relation to the actual amount of infectious HEV ingested, not the quantity of RNA copies ingested.

As it was not possible to differentiate between the two quantities based on the available data, it was decided to perform the HEV QMRA using both the number of RNA copies and the quantity of infectious virus as the microbiological variables, with the latter modelled as an unknown fraction of the former. This allowed us to use the results of the model using RNA copies for comparison and validation against retail sample studies presenting results of diagnostic tests in RNA copies, as well as other QMRAs where the risk outcome was based on RNA rather than infectious virus (Moro 2021, Sarno 2016, Müller 2017). However, for the reasons listed above, it would not be appropriate to use RNA copies to predict the expected number of human infections, and as far as we are aware, no previous studies have made use of HEV infectivity data to this end. As an attempt to address this limitation, the number of human

cases was simulated by running the QMRA assuming that an unknown ‘conversion factor’ can be used to estimate the amount of infectious HEV based on the number of RNA copies. Although inevitably subject to a large amount of uncertainty due to lack of supporting evidence, this approach has the advantage that, as more data becomes available (by either empirical means or expert opinion), the model can be populated to improve our estimates.

Regarding the mathematical functions that can be used to describe thermal inactivation, the *Salmonella* QMRA made use of a simple exponential decay model, which required knowledge of the decimal reduction time (*D*-value) and *z*-value. Data was available for these parameters in several different matrices, specifically water, hide and ground pork. In the case of HEV, a Weibull model of the form (van Boekel 2002, Albert 2005, Buzrul 2022)

$$\log \text{reduction} = at^b \tag{1}$$

was found to be the most appropriate fit for both RNA copy and infectious virus data, with *a* and *b* fitted parameters (note that, for *b* = 1, this reduces to the linear *Salmonella* model). The Weibull model incorporates the physical effect that, as time goes on, the surviving population of microorganisms either may have greater resistance to heat (*b* < 1), or conversely may be more likely to succumb to the effects of heat (*b* > 1).

In general, the data available to model HEV thermal inactivation are limited [see (Scobie 2022) for a recent review]. For HEV RNA copies, data sets were available to model thermal inactivation in either a wild boar liver suspension (Schielke 2011) or a pâté-like preparation (Barnaud 2012). In the wild boar liver suspension, RNA decline was found to be well approximated by a biphasic model with an initial decrease followed by a stationary phase. In particular, the stationary phase was reached after just 1 hour at a refrigeration temperature of 4°C, with a log reduction of 0.34 log₁₀. However, data were only available for heating after 1 and 2 minutes at 70°C, and 1 minute between 75°C and 95°C. Hence, since it was not possible to fit a biphasic model at these temperatures, a Weibull model was chosen to allow for curvature of the inactivation function (while this is insufficient to capture the stationary phase, it is still more representative of the real inactivation kinetics than a linear model). Values for *a* were extracted for each temperature and linearly interpolated for intermediate values, while an estimate for *b* obtained for 70°C was assumed to apply for all other temperatures.

In the case of the pâté-like preparation, log reductions were measured for nine different time-temperature combinations: 62°C at 5, 20 and 120 minutes, as well as 68°C and 71°C at 5, 10 and 20 minutes. No fit to the data was provided, hence it was decided to fit Weibull models to the data at each temperature for consistency with the above. Log reductions at other query temperatures were evaluated by applying a linear fit to the results of these three Weibull models.

Only one study was available for infectious virus, which was performed in cell culture medium (Johne 2016). It was found that the Weibull model provided the best fit function at all temperatures, i.e., there was no stationary phase in contrast to the RNA survival curves (note that this indicates increased stability of HEV RNA to thermal treatment compared to infectious virus). In particular, at 4°C fit parameters *a* = 0.49 and *b* = 0.42 were observed, whereas they were *a* = 2.97 and *b* = 0.79 at 70°C. Data regarding log reductions after heating for one minute at a range of high temperatures up to 90°C were also available. These data were used to extract values for *a* for each temperature, which

were linearly interpolated for intermediate values, while the value for b from the 70°C function was assumed to apply for all other temperatures.

2.1.2.1. Slaughterhouse

Individual parameters: On entry to the slaughterhouse, viral loads in bile, C_{bile} , and faeces, C_{faeces} , of infected pigs, measured in RNA copies per gram, are drawn from probability distributions parameterised from data reported in Salines *et al.* and dos Santos *et al.*, respectively (Salines 2017, dos Santos 2011):

$$C_{\text{faeces}} \sim U(10^4, 10^6) \quad (2)$$

$$C_{\text{bile}} \sim U(10, 10^5) \quad (3)$$

[notation for distributions follows Table 1 of (Swart 2016a)]. Following (Cassin 1998), the ratio of carcasses contaminated with the faeces of HEV-shedding pigs to those free of such contamination was assumed to be $\sim U(2, 3)$ times the ratio of HEV-shedding animals to non-shedders. The density of faecal contamination assigned to such pigs, measured in RNA copies per cm^2 , is drawn randomly from a distribution describing faecal hide contamination as (Crotta 2021)

$$C_{\text{hide,faeces}} \sim U(10^{-4}, 10^{-2}) . \quad (4)$$

This density can be converted into a total load per pig carcass by multiplying by the carcass surface area, which is calculated following (Swart 2016a). While HEV has also been detected in the urine of infected pigs (Salines 2017), this route of hide contamination was not included due to the lack of viral load data. The model assumes that slaughtered pigs are viraemic with probability $P_{\text{viraemic}} = 0.2$ (Grierson 2015), and therefore simulates whether each pig is viraemic or not by means of a Bernoulli trial $B(1, p_{\text{viraemic}})$. If successful, the meat of a viraemic pig is assigned a load

$$C_{\text{meat}} = \rho_{\text{blood}} \times C_{\text{blood}} , \quad (5)$$

where ρ_{blood} and C_{blood} are, respectively, random numbers drawn from distributions describing the residual blood in meat after bleeding in mL/g, and the viral load in blood of viraemic pigs in RNA copies per mL (Crotta 2021):

$$\rho_{\text{blood}} \sim U(2 \times 10^{-3}, 9 \times 10^{-3}) \quad (6)$$

$$C_{\text{blood}} \sim \text{Cumulative}(p, x) , \quad (7)$$

where $p = (0, 0.83, 0.86, 0.89, 0.92, 0.94, 0.97, 1)$ and $x = (49.5, 49.5, 6.1 \times 10^2, 1.3 \times 10^3, 6.3 \times 10^3, 9.9 \times 10^3, 4.3 \times 10^4, 1.3 \times 10^6)$. Here, x denotes the values at which the percentiles p occur, thus defining a cumulative distribution.

As is evident from the above, estimates for the amount of virus that contaminates organs, hide and meat are only available in the literature in terms of RNA copies. At this stage, we assume that the quantity of infectious virus is equal to the quantity of RNA copies, since this is simplest to implement in the simulations. However, this simplification will be correctly accounted for in the dose-response module, Sec. 2.1.2.4., where a ‘conversion factor’ between RNA copies and infectious virus will be

introduced. We now discuss specific modifications to each stage of the slaughterhouse module listed in Table 1.

Bleeding: In contrast to the *Salmonella* QMRA, bleeding is modelled for HEV since blood spillage is an additional source of hide contamination for viraemic pigs. The density of blood spilled over the carcass during bleeding is assumed to be uniform, resulting in an additional contamination density in units of ge/cm^2 given by $C_{\text{hide,blood}} \sim U(10^2, 10^3)$ (Crotta 2021). This is added to the existing faecal contamination $C_{\text{hide,faeces}}$ described in Sec. 2.1.1.1.

Scalding, dehairing, singeing, polishing: The thermal inactivation function for *Salmonella* is replaced by the relevant thermal inactivation functions for both HEV RNA and infectious HEV, which are Weibull models as discussed in Sec. 2.1.2. As the purpose of modelling minced meat for HEV was to demonstrate its low risk compared to liver products (as will be confirmed by our results in Sec. 3.1.), it was decided that it was not necessary to include cross contamination in the model.

Belly opening: In the absence of data, the parameter regarding the fraction of *Salmonella* transferred from skin to hook was used for HEV, under the assumption that such parameters in fact quantify adherence of faecal and blood contamination to the hide, and are not strongly pathogen dependent. In addition to gut puncture, the possibility of gall bladder puncture is also included, with probability $P_{\text{gall bladder}} = 0.019$ (0.016) for middle- (high-) throughput abattoirs, as determined by an expert opinion study (Crotta 2019). The same study was used to parameterise a cumulative distribution for the amount of bile spilled.

Splitting: The parameter regarding the fraction of *Salmonella* transferred to saw was used for HEV.

Trimming: This stage was modelled in the same way as *Salmonella*, except that bile spillage from the belly opening stage was also included in the visible contamination.

Blast chilling: The rapidity with which the product is taken to refrigeration temperature ($\sim 3^\circ\text{C}$ or below in about 90 minutes) results in the formation of ice crystals that can potentially injure or kill bacteria by damaging the cell membrane. While a similar effect could be expected for viruses, we were unable to find data which would allow us to confidently quantify the effect of blast chilling on HEV. Hence, the worst-case assumption was used, i.e., blast chilling has no effect in reducing the load of HEV.

2.1.2.2. Further processing (minced meat)

10,000 portions of minced meat are generated from the half carcasses, as for the *Salmonella* QMRA. For each portion, contamination arises due to possible hide contamination or meat contamination (viraemic pigs).

Various empirical studies regarding the prevalence and amount of HEV RNA found in products at retail have been carried out using quantitative PCR (Boxman 2019, Giannini 2018, Moor 2018, Pallerla 2020, Szabo 2015, Wilhelm 2014), some of which can be compared to the QMRA at this stage. To do this it is necessary to obtain estimates for the PCR limit of detection (LOD) used in these experiments, which is product dependent. For minced meat, we assume the LOD to be the same as for fresh sausage, which has been estimated as (Boxman 2019)

$$\text{LOD}_{\text{MM}} = 1.3 \times 10^3, \quad (8)$$

in units of ge/g. The prevalence of positive portions at retail was then estimated as the percentage of portions whose viral load per gram exceeds the LOD. The distribution of viral loads of these positive portions can also be compared to the distribution of viral loads observed at retail.

2.1.2.3. Consumer cooking (minced meat)

In order that the thermal inactivation functions from Sec. 2.1.2. could be used, it was necessary to assume a temperature of 4°C for each step of transport and storage. For HEV RNA, the duration of transport and storage was deemed sufficiently long to assume that the stationary phase of the biphasic model was reached, corresponding to a log reduction of $0.34 \log_{10}$ during refrigerated storage (Schielke 2011). For infectious virus, where such a biphasic model is not relevant, the total time taken for all three steps was used as the input to the 4°C Weibull model. Preparation of a salad was modelled as for *Salmonella*, using the same transfer coefficients and survival rates under the assumption that such parameters quantify adherence to different surfaces and are not strongly pathogen specific. Cooking of the patty was also modelled as for *Salmonella*, except that the thermal inactivation function was replaced by the relevant thermal inactivation functions for both HEV RNA and infectious HEV.

2.1.2.4. Dose response

In the simulation, the input to the dose response module is the dose of infectious HEV in each portion of each product, $d_{\text{infectious}}$, under the assumption that the quantity of infectious virus is equal to the number of RNA copies at the point of slaughter (see Sec. 2.1.2.). Allowing for the fact that, at slaughter, only an unknown fraction of the RNA copies actually correspond to infectious virus (Duggal 2017), the true dose of infectious HEV in each portion can be expressed as

$$D_{\text{infectious}} = f_{\text{slaughter}} \times d_{\text{infectious}}, \quad (9)$$

where $f_{\text{slaughter}} < 1$ is an unknown 'conversion factor' which applies at the point of slaughter and represents the fraction of RNA copies that correspond to infectious virus in organs, hide and meat of recently slaughtered pigs.

Only two studies have previously attempted to construct dose-response models for HEV. In one, six chimpanzees were inoculated intravenously, with a beta-Poisson model the best fit (Ruchusatsawat 2022), while the other obtained an exponential model based on intravenous inoculation of pigs (Bouwknegt 2011). However, we did not deem these data appropriate for oral inoculation in humans. Instead, following (Müller 2017) we use a threshold dose of $D_{\text{RNA threshold}} = 10^5$ RNA copies (AFFSA 2009, Renou 2014), such that consumption of a portion with a dose above (below) the threshold causes infection with probability 1 (0). By nature of the dose-response experiments, infection necessarily includes asymptomatic cases.

For compatibility with infectious virus data, the threshold must be converted into infectious virus, which we do by analogy of Eq. (9) as

$$D_{\text{infectious threshold}} = f_{\text{dose response}} \times D_{\text{RNA threshold}}, \quad (10)$$

where $f_{\text{dose response}} < 1$ is another unknown ‘conversion factor’ applying to the data used to determine the dose-response model, and represents the fraction of RNA copies that correspond to infectious virus in the doses that were used in the dose-response experiments. Hence, using Eqs. (9) and (10), the threshold value for the variable that is input to the dose-response module, $d_{\text{infectious}}$, is

$$d_{\text{infectious threshold}} = \frac{f_{\text{dose response}}}{f_{\text{slaughter}}} \times D_{\text{RNA threshold}}, \quad (11)$$

i.e., the probability of infection is dependent on the ratio of the conversion factors at the point of slaughter and in the dose-response data. We assume that this is equal to unity, although this is a point of uncertainty that could be further investigated by a sensitivity or scenario analysis. We expect that the ratio is smaller than one, since the doses used to define the dose-response threshold were likely subject to thermal inactivation processes, which degrade infectious virus more quickly than RNA (see Sec. 3.1.2.). It should be noted, however, that although there are two conversion factors in the model, there is only a single degree of freedom, which is the ratio of those two conversion factors.

2.1.2.5. Human cases

In the absence of other data, the amount of minced meat consumed in grams per person per day for MS2 of the *Salmonella* QMRA was assumed to apply for France (EFSA 2010, Vigre 2016). The population of France was obtained from Eurostat.

2.1.3. New HEV-specific products: liver pâté and sliced liver

Besides minced meat, for which the *Salmonella* QMRA could be adapted, two further pathways were constructed for liver products (liver pâté and sliced liver), which are known to be high-risk foods for HEV.

2.1.3.1. Slaughterhouse

On entry to the slaughterhouse, the probability distribution for the viral load in the liver of infected pigs, C_{liver} , measured in RNA copies per gram, was determined by fitting to quantitative PCR measurements taken at French slaughterhouses (Feurer 2018). The data ranged between $3 - 9 \log_{10}$, with $5 - 6 \log_{10}$ the most common category, and the best fit was a generalised Pareto distribution:

$$C_{\text{liver}} \sim \text{GP}(-0.32, 1.74, 3.85). \quad (12)$$

This fit did not account for the fact that the viral load of some infected pigs is likely to lie below the LOD. Hence, since we choose to sample from Eq. (12) for all infected pigs, we have assumed a worst-case scenario for the viral load in pig livers. Because the liver remains inside the carcass until pluck removal, which occurs between belly opening and splitting (Swart 2016a), the viral contamination in livers of infected pigs was assumed to remain unaffected by events along the slaughter line.

2.1.3.2. Further processing

In order that the thermal inactivation functions from Sec. 2.1.2. could be used, it was necessary to assume a temperature of 4°C during transport of livers. For HEV RNA, the duration of transport to further processing was deemed sufficiently long to assume that the stationary phase of the biphasic model was reached, corresponding to a log reduction of $0.34 \log_{10}$ during refrigerated storage (Schielke 2011). The load of HEV RNA and infectious HEV in batches of liver pâté was modelled as

follows. Data regarding the number of livers typically mixed to produce batches was not readily available; instead, a non-systematic survey of mixers and emulsifiers for sale online was carried out. From this, it was assumed that liver pâté was produced at small plants if the total number of livers available was less than 83, with mixing vessel capacity in litres of

$$V_{\text{small}} \sim \text{BP}(6, 12, 30), \quad (13)$$

where BP denotes a beta-PERT distribution, or otherwise large plants with mixing vessel capacity

$$V_{\text{large}} \sim \text{BP}(125, 140, 340). \quad (14)$$

It was also assumed that the vessel runs at 90% of its capacity, while a survey of retail products suggested that the proportion of liver pâté that is liver is given by $f_L \sim U(0.32, 0.41)$. Taking the mean volume of a pig's liver as $V_{\text{liver}} = 1.51$ litres (Niehues 2010), the number of livers per batch was determined by

$$N_{\text{batch}} = \frac{f_{\text{LP}} \times 0.9 \times V_{\text{vessel}}}{V_{\text{liver}}}, \quad (15)$$

where V_{vessel} is either V_{small} or V_{large} depending on the number of livers available. Hence, N_{batch} livers were selected at random for each batch, and the contribution of these livers to the load per gram of the batch was given by f_L multiplied by the mean load per gram of the livers. The model also accounts for a fraction $f_M = 0.12$ of pork meat in each batch of liver pâté, by selecting at random a portion from the minced meat further processing stage (see Sec. 2.1.2.2.). Its contribution per gram of the batch is given by f_M multiplied by its load per gram. After mixing, pre-retail cooking of batches of liver pâté was modelled, with each batch assumed to be cooked at a uniform temperature of $T_{\text{LP}} = 72^\circ\text{C}$, for a total time of $t_{\text{LP}} = 90$ minutes (Steen 2013). During cooking, thermal inactivation is modelled using the Weibull model for RNA in a pâté-like preparation (Barnaud 2012), or the Weibull model for infectious virus (Johns 2016), which were both discussed in Sec. 2.1.2. Finally, 10,000 portions of liver pâté are generated from the batches, with the portion size in grams

$$P_{\text{LP}} \sim \text{BP}(10, 42, 126). \quad (16)$$

10,000 portions of sliced liver are also generated from the livers, with the portion size in grams (Sarno 2016)

$$P_{\text{SL}} \sim \text{BP}(80, 125, 200). \quad (17)$$

As discussed in the previous section for minced meat, direct comparison of RNA loads can be made with retail studies at this stage. The LOD for liver pâté and sliced liver in units of ge/g are (Boxman 2019)

$$\text{LOD}_{\text{LP}} = 1.3 \times 10^2 \quad (18)$$

$$\text{LOD}_{\text{SL}} = 3.8 \times 10^3. \quad (19)$$

2.1.3.3. Consumer cooking

As liver pâté is a ready-to-eat product, it is not modelled in this module. The amount of infectious virus present in sliced liver portions is reduced during transport and storage according to the 4°C Weibull function, but there is no further reduction of HEV RNA at this stage, since the stationary phase was already reached in the further processing module. By approximating liver pieces as cylindrical patties, it was possible to model the spatial temperature distribution of sliced liver during cooking in the same way as minced meat patties in the *Salmonella* QMRA, which was described in Table 1 (EFSA 2010, Swart 2016b). The following parameters were updated for liver: density $\rho_{\text{liver}} = 1070 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ (Niehues 2010), specific heat capacity $c_{\text{liver}} = 3252 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, as well as thermal conductivity $\lambda_{\text{liver}} = 0.515 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The liver is assumed to be cooked from chilled, i.e., 4°C, at a pan-frying temperature of 180°C and with an ambient temperature of 25°C. The product is turned over halfway through cooking. The cooked portion is assumed to be 1cm thick with a radius of 8cm, which corresponds to a mass of approximately 200g, i.e., the maximum portion size in Eq. (17). Log reductions from this portion size are assumed to apply to all portion sizes. The total cooking time in minutes was drawn from a discrete general (DG) distribution

$$t_{\text{SL}} \sim \text{DG}[(1.5, 2, 11), (0.35, 0.65)], \quad (20)$$

which was parameterised as follows. A previous study has estimated that 19 – 52% of livers served commercially fail to reach 70°C (Jones 2016). As this range is an uncertainty distribution, and we do not include uncertainty in the QMRA, we take the midpoint of this range, i.e., 35%. According to the cooking model for sliced liver, the time taken to reach 70°C in the core was approximately 2 minutes, hence we assume that 35% of consumers cook sliced liver for less than 2 minutes. It was also determined, from a non-systematic review of recipes, that the minimum and maximum cooking times for sliced liver are 90 seconds and 11 minutes, respectively (recommended cooking times for sliced liver bought from retail are around 8 minutes). For each total cooking time t_{SL} , log reductions were assigned by using the spatial temperature distribution in combination with the Weibull models for HEV RNA in a wild boar liver suspension as well as infectious virus (see Sec. 2.1.2.).

2.1.3.4. Dose response

The same dose-response function was used as for HEV in minced meat, since the dose-response model only depends on the pathogen.

2.1.3.5. Human cases

It was not possible to obtain relevant data for the amount of liver pâté and sliced liver consumed in France, so UK data were used as a proxy (FSA 2022). In grams per person per day, the amount of liver pâté consumed is

$$s_{\text{LP}} = 0.56, \quad (21)$$

while the amount of sliced liver consumed is

$$s_{\text{SL}} = 0.054. \quad (22)$$

The portion size used was taken as the mean of the distributions of Eqs. (16) and (17) introduced above.

2.2. Biosecurity measures

The *Salmonella* and HEV QMRAs were used to simulate the effect of the biosecurity measures listed in Table 2. With the exception of anal bunging, which was a slaughterhouse intervention modelled mechanistically by setting the amount of faeces extruded in the dehairing and polishing stages to zero, all biosecurity measures were modelled by estimating the reduction in prevalence in slaughter-age finisher pigs due to the biosecurity measure using risk ratios.

These were selected as follows: A catalogue of biosecurity measures for *Salmonella* and HEV, which was collated from the literature, was produced by work package 5 of the BIOPIGEE project. This was filtered for studies where a risk ratio was available and suggested that the biosecurity measure had a positive effect in reducing the prevalence of the pathogen in finisher pigs. The remaining measures were then further filtered based on availability of data for the cost-benefit analysis, leaving 9 measures for *Salmonella* (in addition to anal bunging) and 3 for HEV.

Each scenario was simulated by using the risk ratio to calculate the slaughter-pig prevalence in that scenario, assuming 100% uptake of the biosecurity measure, while accounting for the fact that some farms are already implementing the measure. This prevalence was used as the input to the QMRA, in replacement of the baseline prevalence. Specifically, if farms implementing (not implementing) a biosecurity measure have on-farm prevalence p_b (p_n), the risk ratio (RR) is defined as

$$RR = p_b/p_n, \quad (23)$$

assuming that the observational unit used to determine the risk ratio was individual pigs. In the case of 100% uptake, the country-wide prevalence would be p_b , but this cannot be determined from Eq. (23) since p_n is unknown. However, the baseline prevalence for a country p is known, and can be expressed as

$$p = f_b p_b + (1 - f_b) p_n, \quad (24)$$

where f_b is the proportion of farms currently implementing the biosecurity measure, which is known from work package 2 of the BIOPIGEE project and listed in Table 2. By substituting Eq. (23), p_n can be eliminated and one finds

$$p_b = \frac{p}{f_b + \frac{1-f_b}{RR}} \quad (25)$$

as the input to the QMRA for each scenario. Only four risk ratios were available with pig as the observational unit, which are marked with an asterisk (*) in Table 2.

For all other risk ratios, where the observational unit was not pigs (e.g., field studies may have been based on positivity of herds or farms instead of individual pigs), Eq. (25) can not be used because the pig risk ratio is unknown. However, when a risk ratio is known for an observational unit other than pig, it can be shown that this is the minimum possible pig risk ratio. Hence, in this case the risk ratio for the observational unit can be used in Eq. (25) as a best-case scenario. From the perspective of the economic analysis this is still useful to consider, since if a biosecurity measure is not cost effective in

the best-case scenario, it will not be cost-effective when the correct pig risk ratio is applied. However, further investigation is required if a best-case scenario is found to be cost effective.

Table 2: Summary of biosecurity measures implemented in the Salmonella and HEV QMRAs. Risk ratios marked with an asterisk () are based on studies where the observational unit was pigs, while all other risk ratios are best-case estimates based on other observational units.*

Scenario	Biosecurity measure	Description (where necessary)	Finisher pig risk ratio, RR	Proportion of farms already implementing biosecurity measure, f_b
Salmonella				
1	Vaccination	Vaccination of sows and piglets	0.3632	0
2	Pen C&D	Always clean and disinfect farrowing pen before new sow moves in	0.4654	0.606
3	Farmer rodent control	Rodent control on farm by farmers	0.5414	0.7397
4	Professional rodent control	Rodent control on farm by professional company	0.5414	0.4895
5	Boot C&D	Use of disinfection baths for boots between farm sections	0.7994	0.267
6	Organic acid in feed of weaners	N/A	0.5282*	0.4348
7	Organic acid in water of weaners	N/A	0.25*	0.0496
8	Organic acid in feed of finishers	N/A	0.7834*	0.3839
9	Wheel C&D	Cleaning and disinfection of wheels of external vehicles visiting farm	0.4524	Austria: 0.0005 UK: 0.73
10	Anal bunging	Anal bunging of 100% of carcasses on slaughter line	N/A	0
HEV				
1	Specific boots	Specific boots for each farm section	0.1613	0.2697
2	Reduced mingling	< 25% cross-fostering rate for piglets	0.3704*	0.6014
3	Vehicle C&D	Disinfection of external vehicles visiting farm using a sanitary ford	0.3917	0.73

2.3. Model implementation

The *Salmonella* and HEV QMRAs were written in MATLAB version R2022a (MATLAB 2022). Baseline models, as well as each biosecurity measure scenario, were executed for 10,000 iterations, with 10,000 portions per iteration. This was sufficient to ensure convergence, as tested by plotting running means of $P_{infection}$ for each product versus the number of iterations.

Natural variation is included in the model by sampling from the variability distributions introduced in previous sections. This includes variation between iterations, for example drawing different slaughterhouses from the HEV farm model, as well as variation within iterations, such as different

consumer cooking times for sliced liver. However, it was chosen not to explicitly include parameter uncertainty in the model, but instead investigate this through a sensitivity analysis.

Besides variability and parameter uncertainty, the stochasticity of MC simulations is a source of statistical uncertainty — each MC simulation has a different random seed and so produces different outputs — which can be reduced by running the model for more iterations. To measure this effect, each simulation was divided into a sample of 100 independent simulations, and the sample mean μ and standard deviation σ of human case numbers were calculated. Invoking the central limit theorem, the sample mean was assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean μ and standard deviation $\frac{\sigma}{10}$, allowing 5th and 95th percentiles for human case numbers to be extracted.

As described in Sec. 2.1., the *Salmonella* QMRA was parameterised considering data for Austria and the UK, while the HEV QMRA was informed by prevalence data for France.

3. Results

In this section, QMRA results for *Salmonella* in Austria and the UK, as well as for HEV in France, are presented. We first focus on the baseline model, which estimates real-world human case numbers due to consumption of the selected pork products. In the subsequent section, these results are compared to hypothetical case numbers that could be achieved if the biosecurity measures listed in Table 2 are implemented.

3.1. Baseline model

3.1.1. *Salmonella*

Fig 2. shows histograms of the probability of infection over all iterations for each of the three product types considered, for Austria (left panel) and the UK (right panel). These histograms reflect the variability of the model parameters, and hence the model output, from one iteration to the next.

Fig. 2. Histograms of probability of infection, $P_{infection}$, when consuming a portion of fermented sausage, minced meat or pork cut in Austria (left panel) and the UK (right panel).

The baseline estimates of the mean probability of infection over all iterations, $\langle P_{infection} \rangle$, for Austria are 2.24×10^{-6} for fermented sausage, 1.19×10^{-6} for minced meat and 9.39×10^{-7} for pork cuts,

whereas for the UK they are 6.06×10^{-5} for fermented sausage, 3.20×10^{-5} for minced meat and 2.65×10^{-5} for pork cuts. For both countries, the products with the highest and lowest probability of infection are fermented sausage and pork cuts, respectively. For each product type, the estimated value for $\langle P_{\text{infection}} \rangle$ is between one and two orders of magnitude larger in the UK compared to Austria. Note that this largely reflects the difference in *Salmonella* prevalence amongst pigs in the two countries, which is a factor of around 16 times larger in the UK (see Sec. 2.1), although there are other parameter differences in the model that contribute to this effect.

The expected number of human cases in Austria is 448 (95% CI 415, 481) for fermented sausage, 72 (95% CI 67, 77) for minced meat, and 635 (95% CI 604, 667) for pork cuts, whereas for the UK they are 6,126 (95% CI 6,029, 6,223) for fermented sausage, 15,918 (95% CI 15,688, 16,147) for minced meat and 13,966 (95% CI 13,799, 14,133) for pork cuts. Hence, the case load is dictated by consumption patterns as well as $\langle P_{\text{infection}} \rangle$; despite being the riskiest product in the UK, fermented sausage has the lowest case load, since it is consumed less often compared to minced meat and pork cuts. Similarly, UK minced meat cases are more than 200 times those in Austria, even though the probability of infection per portion is only 27 times larger. This is because, according to the model parameters, the number of minced meat portions consumed per year in the UK is over 8 times more than in Austria.

3.1.2. HEV

As discussed in Sec. 2.1.2., an important (but difficult) challenge regarding HEV contamination data is to identify the proportion of detected RNA copies that represents actual infectious virus. Hence, this section is divided into two parts: Results considering only the presence and quantity of HEV RNA in food at retail, for the purposes of model validation and comparison, are first reported in Sec. 3.2.1.1. Following this, QMRA results estimating human case numbers, which are based on assumptions regarding the proportion of HEV RNA that is infectious, are reported in Sec. 3.2.1.2.

3.2.1.1. RNA copies in food at retail

Intermediate QMRA results for HEV, showing the amount of HEV RNA detected in each food product at the end of the further processing module (as would be measured at a retail premises), are summarised in Table 3. The results are compared with recent surveys that have investigated the prevalence and load of HEV RNA in similar products sold at retail.

Table 3. Prevalence and mean load of HEV RNA for liver pâté, minced meat and sliced liver at the end of further processing according to the HEV QMRA, as well as recent surveys conducted in the Netherlands (Boxman 2019) and Germany (Pallerla 2020).

Product	Prevalence (%)			Mean HEV RNA load (\log_{10} ge/g)	
	QMRA	Netherlands	Germany	QMRA	Netherlands
Liver pâté	8.6	68.9	15	2.6	4
Minced meat	0.2	0	0	3.2	N/A
Sliced liver	5.7	12.7	5	4.9	5.5

The HEV QMRA captures the trend observed in both retail studies: The prevalence in liver pâté is larger compared to sliced liver, with the prevalence of minced meat close to zero, while RNA loads observed in sliced liver are higher compared to liver pâté. These results are to be expected if the LOD is not taken

into account since, when livers are mixed to produce batches of liver pâté, one expects the number of contaminated batches to exceed the number of contaminated livers (only one infected liver is required to contaminate a whole batch), albeit each with a diluted load. However, because the LOD must be taken into account, these results are not trivial. For example, it could have been possible that the mixing step reduced the majority of batches below the LOD, leading to a smaller prevalence for liver pâté compared to sliced liver.

3.2.1.2. Probability of infection and human cases

For liver pâté and minced meat, the probability of infection was zero and hence the expected number of human cases was also zero. This is explained by the effect of thermal treatment during processing, where the time-temperature parameters for MM and LP led to total inactivation of infectious HEV for LP and a very low residual infectious viral load for MM. This is despite the presence of appreciable levels of HEV RNA in LP and highlights the non-equivalence between RNA copies and infectious virus. Note that, for both HEV and *Salmonella*, contamination levels on the hide are reduced to trace amounts on the slaughter line. The lack of risk associated with MM for HEV compared with *Salmonella* therefore reflects the inability of HEV to replicate outside of host cells in the subsequent steps, whereas as bacterial growth of *Salmonella* can return it to appreciable levels

Considering the dose-response threshold of $5 \log_{10}$ ge/portion, the only product leading to a non-zero probability of infection was sliced liver (Fig. 3.). As the probability of infection for each portion is modelled as a binary outcome equal to zero or one (see Sec. 2.1.2.4.), the possible values of $P_{\text{infection}}$ for each iteration are integer multiples of 10^{-4} , since 10,000 portions per iteration are simulated. The number of portions leading to infection ranged from a minimum of 0 to a maximum of ~ 35 across all iterations, leading to a mean value of $\langle P_{\text{infection}} \rangle = 7.34 \times 10^{-5}$ and an estimated number of human cases of 755 (95% CI 723, 787).

Fig. 3. Histogram of probability of infection, $P_{\text{infection}}$, when consuming a portion of sliced liver in France. As the probability of infection for each portion is modelled as a binary outcome (0,1), and 10,000 portions per iteration are simulated, the possible values of $P_{\text{infection}}$ for each iteration are integer multiples of 10^{-4} . The tail of the distribution extends beyond 8×10^{-4} but the x axis has been cut to clearly show the important features of the distribution

3.2. Biosecurity measures

As explained in Sec. 2.2., the effect of implementing each biosecurity measure (except for anal bunting) was simulated by using the risk ratio to calculate the slaughter-pig prevalence assuming 100%
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uptake of the biosecurity measure under investigation. It is important to reiterate that, when using a risk ratio derived from a study where the observational unit was not the individual pig, i.e., all risk ratios in Table 2 not marked by an asterisk, the estimates are representative of a best-case scenario.

3.2.1. *Salmonella*

The estimated effects of the biosecurity measures against *Salmonella* calculated as described in section 2.2. are presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 4. Bar chart showing expected number of human cases associated with consumption of fermented sausage, minced meat and pork cuts in Austria (left panel) and the UK (right panel). Red error bars indicate 5th and 95th percentiles. B = Baseline, 1 = Vaccination, 2 = Pen C&D, 3 = Farmer rodent control, 4 = Professional rodent control, 5 = Boot C&D, 6 = Organic acid in feed of weaners, 7 = Organic acid in water of weaners, 8 = Organic acid in feed of finishers, 9 = Wheel C&D, 10 = Anal bunging.

The biosecurity measure resulting in the highest reduction of human cases was the use of anal bunging to prevent the spread of faeces during slaughter, which had a reduction of ~95% from the baseline values for Austria and the UK when considering minced meat and fermented sausages, and ~90% when considering pork chops. The second and third most effective measures were the use of organic acid in water of weaners, and vaccination of sows and piglets, respectively. When tested, the effects of these control measures resulted in reductions of ~73% and ~63% from the baseline human cases for both Austria and the UK across all products. The least effective measure was boot C&D, resulting in a reduction of between 13 – 15% (depending on the product) from the baseline value for both countries.

3.2.2. HEV

The estimated effects of the HEV biosecurity measures, simulated as described in Sec. 2.2., are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Bar chart showing expected number of human cases associated with consumption of sliced liver in France. Red error bars indicate 5th and 95th percentiles. B = Baseline, 1 = Specific boots, 2 = Reduced mingling, 3 = Vehicle C&D.

For HEV, the biosecurity measure resulting in the largest reduction of human cases was the use of specific boots for each farm section, resulting in a ~80% reduction from the baseline number of human cases. This was followed by reduced mingling of piglets from different pens (~60% reduction) and vehicle C&D (~35% reduction).

4. Discussion

Activities carried out as part of this deliverable consisted of the development of QMRA models to allow estimation of the expected number of human cases of salmonellosis and hepatitis E due to the consumption of pork products, as well as the effectiveness of a range of control measures. Results of this model will be used to inform an economic model that aims to assess the cost effectiveness of the different control measures (deliverable D-JRP21-WP4.16).

As explained in Sec. 2.1.2., results for both *Salmonella* and HEV were obtained by adapting the farm-to-consumption QMRA for *Salmonella* developed for EFSA (EFSA 2010, Snary 2016). This previous QMRA was framed as a generic model that could account for differences in pig production, slaughterhouse practices and consumption patterns across EU Member States (MS), and was used to simulate the impact of control measures and hypothetical reductions in slaughter-pig prevalence on the risk of human infection. As such, the adaptations required for this work in relation to *Salmonella* were reduced to an upgrade of the initial prevalence of infected pigs and consumption data for the two countries under consideration, which were Austria and the UK.

Adapting the *Salmonella* QMRA for HEV required careful consideration of the biological differences between the two pathogens and the introduction of several assumptions to overcome key data gaps. Running the HEV QMRA model by separately considering two microbiological variables (RNA copies and infectious HEV) was judged as the most transparent option, allowing us to highlight how these two quantities have a substantially different meaning in terms of the risk to consumers. Indeed, the results of our HEV QMRA imply that although a food product such as liver pâté may appear highly contaminated when considering RNA copies, in fact it could contain zero infectious virus and hence be of little risk to the consumer.

By running the HEV QMRA using RNA copies as the microbiological variable, we were able to compare intermediate QMRA results (at the end of the further processing module) with experimental data in the literature. It was found that the simulated load of HEV RNA per gram of liver pâté and sliced liver was comparable to the load reported by Boxman *et al.* as part of a monitoring study for HEV RNA in pork liver and meat products on the Dutch market (Boxman 2019). Although prevalence estimates for the products are not directly comparable across studies because the prevalence of infected pigs (and thus contaminated livers entering the pork supply chain) is different across countries, the fact that the load data are similar provides some reassurance with regards to the validity of the model.

When the QMRA for HEV was run using infectious virus as the microbiological variable, the only product with a nonzero probability of infection was sliced liver, where the predicted number of human cases was 755 (95% CI 723, 786). It should be noted that this figure includes asymptomatic infections – HEV cases in healthy individuals rarely result in severe disease. As discussed in Sec. 3.2.1.2., the reason for zero simulated human cases due to consumption of liver pâté and minced meat can be attributed to the time and temperature parameters during processing, which led to total thermal inactivation of infectious HEV in the case of liver pâté, and left only a residual HEV load for minced meat which was insufficient to cause infection given the dose-response threshold.

One of the major challenges when developing the HEV QMRA was to model the actual amount of infectious viral particles, given mostly data regarding the amount of HEV RNA as quantified by means of RT-PCR. As explained in Sec. 2.1.2.4., this limitation was handled by introducing so-called ‘conversion factors’ between HEV RNA and infectious virus at two different stages of the model: one at the point of slaughter $f_{\text{slaughter}}$, which converted RNA loads in organs, hide and meat into infectious virus, and another in the dose-response model $f_{\text{dose response}}$, which converted the dose-response threshold value from RNA copies into infectious virus. Although the current scientific evidence does not allow one to confidently establish the numerical values of these conversion factors, it was in fact shown that the only degree of freedom in the model was their ratio $f_{\text{dose response}}/f_{\text{slaughter}}$, which we assumed to be unity.

In relation to the actual amount of HEV ingested, another source of uncertainty relates to the inactivation of the virus as a function of time and temperature in complex food matrices. As described in Sec. 2.1.2., the lack of data regarding thermal inactivation in different matrices is a limitation of our model. This is particularly relevant for the modelling of infectious virus because the presence of fats, proteins and minerals surrounding virus particles is known to result in increased resistance to heat (Yunoki 2008, Barnaud 2012, EFSA 2017). For example, our thermal inactivation model for infectious HEV implies reduction below detectable levels after two minutes at 70°C in cell culture medium, whereas from the study of (Barnaud 2012) it can be inferred that infectious HEV may survive heating at 71°C for between 5–20 minutes in a pâté-like preparation (Advisory Committee On The Microbiological Safety of Food 2015), which is significantly longer (note that this also exceeds the commonly quoted cooking recommendation of two minutes at 70°C). Hence, it is likely that our QMRA underestimates the quantity of infectious virus that is able to survive thermal treatment in liver and meat products. Although this is unlikely to affect our prediction of zero human cases for liver pâté and minced meat, which undergo long thermal treatments, we expect that the number of sliced liver cases has been underestimated in this regard.

Three previous risk assessments estimating the risk of human exposure to HEV through consumption of pork products can be found in the literature (Moro 2021, Müller 2017, Sarno 2016), two of which have attempted to estimate the expected number of human cases (Moro 2021, Müller 2017). In both, it was assumed that the amount of RNA copies translated into the amount of infectious HEV as a 1:1 ratio [in (Müller 2017) it was further assumed that only 1% of the consumers exposed to 10^5 gc/portion became ill], and the effect of thermal treatment on infectious HEV in terms of log reductions was equal to that observed for RNA copies. Comparison of the risk estimates between studies is challenging due to major differences in the products being considered, consumption patterns and the assumptions made. However, a key difference between our model and those available in the literature is that our QMRA represents, to our knowledge, the first attempt to quantitatively model all steps affecting the presence and amount of HEV from farm to consumption in a highly mechanistic way. While such a detailed model comes at the expense of requiring large amounts of data for parameterisation, it has the advantage that it can be used to simulate not only the expected number of human cases arising from the consumption of different pork products, but also the effect of control measures applied in one or more steps along the food chain. Additionally, modelling the fate of HEV from farm to consumption in such a mechanistic manner has allowed us to highlight the most pressing knowledge gaps that, despite the considerable amount of research carried out on HEV in the past few decades, still prevent accurate estimation of the risk to consumers. It is hoped that our model can be updated with more accurate parameters as these become available.

The estimated effects of the farm-level biosecurity measures considered for *Salmonella* in this deliverable showed encouraging reductions in the expected number of human cases of salmonellosis. However, the option that emerged as most effective was the use of anal bunting to prevent the spread of potentially contaminated faeces during slaughter, as was previously suggested by (Hill 2016). Considerable reduction in human cases was also found for the three HEV biosecurity measures, with the most and least effective being the use of specific boots for each farm section and disinfection of external vehicles visiting the farm using a sanitary ford, respectively. As the latter applies during transport, it can be thought of as preventing the introduction of HEV from pigs on other farms, while the former applies at the farm level and hence can be thought of as minimising the within-herd spread.

When evaluating the cost-effectiveness of the biosecurity measures, there are several features in our study that should be considered. Firstly, although some measures such as vaccination are pathogen specific, others such as boot C&D are likely to be effective against both *Salmonella* and HEV (possibly to different extents), since both pathogens are characterised by a faecal-oral route of transmission. Hence, when multiple pathogens are considered in the cost-benefit analysis, an increased benefit can be realised for the same cost. For this reason it would have been useful to consider the same set of biosecurity measures for both pathogens, but unfortunately the data available in work package 5 meant that this was not possible.

In addition, it should be emphasised that there are two important aspects to our QMRA, which are both prevalence and the load of a pathogen. While our approach using risk ratios accounts for changes in the former when a biosecurity measure is implemented, it fails to account for the latter, which is sometimes relevant for certain control measures. For example, vaccination or use of organic acids in water or feed have been shown to impact the amount of *Campylobacter* in the intestines of broilers (Nauta 2022), while use of organic acids is known to reduce the amount of *Salmonella* shed in faeces

(Gavin 2018), which would in turn reduce the contamination level of carcasses. In this regard, the reduction in the number of human cases for such measures is likely to be underestimated.

Finally, eight risk ratios shown in Table 2 were derived from studies where the observational unit was not the individual pig, meaning that our estimates in those cases reflect a best-case scenario. While this represents a limitation due to data availability, we believe our results are still informative since if a biosecurity measure is found not to be cost effective in the best-case scenario, it certainly won't be in general. On the other hand, if a best-case scenario is found to be cost effective, our model can be easily updated with the appropriate risk ratio should this become available.

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